

Expression of P53 and EGFR in Squamous Cell Carcinoma of Head and Neck

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Abstract:

Background: The process of oral carcinogenesis encompasses multiple proto-oncogenes and tumor suppressor genes, including p16, cyclin D1, p53, and EGFR. A significant player in this context is the TP53 gene, situated on chromosome 17p, which is susceptible to frequent mutations during human carcinogenesis. This study aims to assess the immunohistochemical overexpression of p53 in cases of head and neck squamous cell carcinoma (HNSCC) and its connection to various clinicopathologic features and survival rates.

Methods: Tissue samples from head and neck lesions were fixed in formalin, processed, and embedded in paraffin. Sections were stained with Hematoxylin and Eosin (H&E) for routine diagnosis. Selective sections were stained with immunohistochemistry markers p53 and EGFR to assess their expression in squamous cell carcinoma of the head and neck. Tumors were graded according to Broder's criteria.

Results: The expression of p53 in the oral cavity was showed in 43 (66.15%) cases, out of these 3 cases (4.61%) showed strong p53 positivity, 14 cases (21.53%) showed moderate p53 positivity and 26 cases (40%) showed weak p53 positivity. The expression of EGFR in the oral cavity showed in 43 (66.15%) cases, out of these, 4 cases (6.15%) were showed strong EGFR positivity, 14 cases (21.53%) were showed moderate EGFR positivity and 25 cases (38.46%) were showed weak EGFR positivity.

Conclusion: The clinical significance of p53 and EGFR alterations in relation to HNSCC treatment is an area of active research. However, several studies have indicated that p53 and EGFR expression represent good prognostic parameters and can be used to predict the response to chemoradiation therapy.

Keywords: Head and Neck Squamous Cell Carcinoma (HNSCC), epidermal growth factor receptor (EGFR), p53 oncosuppressor gene.

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Introduction

Head and neck squamous cell carcinoma is the sixth most common cancer worldwide, with 8,90,000 new cases and 4,50,000 deaths in 2018. The incidence of HNSCC continues to rise and is anticipated to rise by 30% (that is, 1.08 million new cases annually) by 2030 (GLOBOCAN) [1]. HNSCC is the sixth leading cancer by incidence worldwide. The male-to-female ratio ranges from 2:1 to 4:1. However, the ratio is the reverse in India where the reported male-to-female ratio is 1:2. [2] It is the most common cancer in India with a large fraction of cases occurring in males in their productive years of life. Head and neck cancers are a significant problem in our country constituting approximately one-third of all cancer cases. [3] In general, men are at 2–4-fold higher risk than women for developing HNSCC. The median age of diagnosis for non-virally associated HNSCC is 66 years, whereas the median age of diagnosis for HPV-associated oropharyngeal cancer and Epstein–Barr virus (EBV)-associated nasopharyngeal cancer

is ~53 years and ~50 years, respectively. [1] Males are affected more often than females because of heavier indulgence in both tobacco and alcohol habits in most countries: in India, the highest rates of intraoral cancer may be found in women who chew tobacco heavily. The GLOBOCAN project estimated 3,00,373 new cases in 2012, with a global age-standardized incidence rate of 14.0 cases per 1,00,000 population per year and a global mortality rate of 1.9 deaths per 1,00,000 population per year. A high incidence of oral cancer is found in southern Asia (e.g., India; Pakistan; Sri Lanka; and Taiwan, China), with age-standardized incidence rates of > 10 cases per 1,00,000 population per year in parts of India. [2]. Oral carcinogenesis involves several proto-oncogenes and tumor suppressor genes, such as p16, cyclin D1, p53, and EGFR. The TP53 gene, a tumor suppressor located on chromosome 17p, is frequently affected by mutations in human carcinogenesis. These mutations lead to the

accumulation of the altered protein inside cancer cells, resulting in immunohistochemical overexpression. Notably, in oral squamous cell carcinoma (OSCC), the overexpression of p53 is considered an indicator of poor prognosis. [4] Additionally, this overexpression can reduce the sensitivity of tumor cells to chemotherapeutic drugs. [5] Therefore, our study aims to assess the immunohistochemical overexpression of p53 in cases of head and neck squamous cell carcinoma (HNSCC) and its connection to various clinicopathologic features and survival rates. The findings from this research can aid in devising therapeutic protocols specifically tailored for the loco-regional population.

Material and Methods

This cross-sectional study was conducted in the Department of Pathology, Kakatiya Medical College and Mahatma Gandhi Memorial Hospital, Warangal, Telangana. Institutional Ethical approval was obtained for the study. Successive biopsy samples of the Head and neck region were included in the study based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Inclusion Criteria

All the cases of squamous cell carcinomas of the Head & Neck coming to the Department of Pathology, Mahatma Gandhi Memorial Hospital, Warangal will be included in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

All Infectious conditions, Inflammatory lesions, and other tumors are to be excluded from the study.

Incision and excision biopsy specimens from the Head and Neck lesions will be fixed in formalin, routine tissue processing done, and paraffin-embedded blocks will be sectioned and will be routinely stained with Hematoxylin and Eosin. Selective representative sections are taken for immunohistochemistry staining with markers p53 and EGFR and their expression will be seen in biopsies of squamous cell carcinoma of head and neck. Specimens received were fixed in 10% (v/v) formalin. After conventional processing, paraffin sections of 3-4µm thickness were stained by Haematoxylin and Eosin (H&E) for diagnosing, grading, and staging of the tumor. Tumors were graded according to Broder's criteria into well, moderate, and poorly differentiated as given in Table 1

Table 1: Broder's Criteria for Grading SCC

Grade	Percentage Of Undifferentiated Cells
Well-differentiated	<25%
Moderately-differentiated	<50%
Poorly-differentiated	<75%
Anaplastic/pleomorphic	>75%

Tissue cores of 3 mm in diameter from representative areas of formalin-fixed paraffin-embedded (FFPE) tumor blocks were taken using a disposable skin biopsy punch. The cores were then embedded in paraffin in planned order and made into paraffin blocks of 5 tissue cores each. 4µm sections from paraffin-embedded tissues were taken on the glass slides which were precoated with poly-lysine for IHC.

IHC Staining of TMA Sections: The sections were deparaffinized and dehydrated, and endogenous peroxidase quenching was done with 3% H₂O₂. Antigen retrieval was done by microwave oven (heat-induced epitope retrieval) with Tris buffer (1.21 g Tris hydroxymethyl methylamine and 3.75 mg EDTA in 1000ml distilled water). Incubated with primary antibody for cyclin D1 (Cell Signalling, Ontario, Canada) which is ready to use, at room temperature in a humidified chamber for 30 minutes. The sections were washed with TBS buffer (9.6 g of Trishydroxymethylmethylaminic

and 8.6 g of NaCl in 1000 ml of distilled water). The sections were then incubated with the Abcam (clone: EP272Y catalog No. AB227561) Rabbit Monoclonal Antibody (Biocare) for cyclin D1 for detection of antigen-antibody reactions for 30 minutes. Sections were visualized with DAB (Dako labeled) for the detection of enzymatic activity. Counterstaining was done with Mayer's hematoxylin. Dehydration was done in ascending grades of alcohol, and xylene. Sections were mounted using DPX and cover glass.

Morphological evaluation of P53 and EGFR in HNSCC: Slides were evaluated using light microscopy. P53 and EGFR stain neoplastic cells with varying intensity. The total score (TS) was calculated by multiplying ES with IS. Which was graded as given in Table 2. The percentage of cells stained was scored as Expression Score (ES) (Table 3). The total score (TS) was calculated by multiplying ES with IS. Which was graded as given in Table 4.

Table 2: The staining intensity was recorded as the Intensity score.

Intensity score (IS)	Intensity of staining
1	Mild
2	Moderate
3	Strong

Table 3: The percentage of cells stained was scored as Expression Score (ES)

Expression score (ES)	Percentage of cells stained
1	1% - 25%
2	26% - 50%
3	51% - 75%
4	>75%

Table 4: The staining intensity was recorded as the Intensity score.

Total score (TS)	Grading
1 - 4 points	Weak
5 - 8 points	Moderate
9 - 12 points	Strong

Statistical analysis: All the data collected was uploaded to an MS Excel spreadsheet and analyzed by SPSS version 21 in Windows format. The continuous variables were represented as mean, Standard deviations, and percentages. The categorical variables were represented by p-values calculated by the Chi-Square test and a p-value of (<0.05) is considered as significant.

Results

In this study the age group ranges from 21 years to 80 years of age, the group with the highest incidence of HNSCC is 41 - 60 years consisting of 39 cases, and the lowest in the age group of 21 - 40 years, with 5 cases. The mean age of the cohort was 52.15 ± 5.5 years. Out of the total cases, 58 were males in the age group of 21 - 80 years with the highest has been in 41 - 60 years (34 cases). Females have 7 cases with the highest being in 41 - 60 years (5 cases). The distribution of the cases are depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Showing the age-wise and sex-wise distribution of cases included in the study.

Out of the total 65 cases of SCC, 43 cases (66.15%) arise in the oral cavity, 12 cases (18.46%) arise in the oropharynx, 7 cases (10.76%) arise in the laryngopharynx, 1 case each from the nasal cavity and forehead. We also saw 1 case in conjunctiva

with a male. Out of the 65 cases of HNSCC 50(76.9%), were well-differentiated, 13 cases (20%) cases were moderately differentiated, and 2 cases (3.1%) were poorly differentiated SCCs on H&E staining.

P53 was expressed as nuclear positivity in all the cases of HNSCC, with 4 cases (6.2%) showing strong positivity, 21 cases (32.3%) showing moderate positivity, 40 cases (61.5%) showing weak positivity, out of 40 cases 2 cases are reported as moderately differentiated SCCs on H&E but on immunohistochemistry of p53 reported as well differentiated SCCs with weak positivity.

Table 5: Cases distribution based on the site of SCC and grade of p53 expression

P53 expression Site of tumor	Weak N (%)	Moderate N (%)	Strong N (%)	Total N (%)
Oral cavity	26 (40%)	14 (21.53%)	3 (4.61%)	43 (66.15%)
Oropharynx	8 (12.3%)	4 (6.15%)	0(0.0%)	12 (18.46%)
Laryngopharynx	5 (7.69%)	1 (1.53%)	1 (1.53%)	7 (10.76%)
Nasal cavity	1 (1.53%)	0(0.0%)	0(0.0%)	1 (1.53%)
Conjunctiva	0(0.0%)	1(1.53%)	0(0.0%)	1 (1.53%)
Forehead	0(0.0%)	1(1.53%)	0(0.0%)	1(1.53%)
Total	40 (61.5%)	21 (32.3%)	4 (6.2%)	65 (100%)

The expression of p53 in the oral cavity was shown in 43 (66.15%) cases, out of these 3 cases (4.61%) showed strong p53 positivity, 14 cases (21.53%) showed moderate p53 positivity and 26 cases (40%) showed weak p53 positivity. In the oropharynx, p53 expression was shown in 12 cases (18.46%), out of these, 4 cases (6.15%) showed moderate p53 positivity, and 8 cases (12.3%) showed weak p53 positivity. In the Laryngopharynx p53 expression showed in 7 cases

(10.76%), out of these, 1 case (1.53%) showed strong p53 positivity, 1 case (1.53%) showed moderate p53 positivity and 5 cases (7.69%) showed weak p53 positivity. In the nasal cavity p53 expression showed in 1 case (1.53%), which was weak p53 positivity. In the conjunctiva, p53 expression showed in 1 case (1.53%), which was moderate p53 positivity. In Forehead, p53 expression showed in 1 case (1.53%), which was moderate p53 positivity.

Table 6: Case distribution based on Total Score of p53 with tumor grade

P53 expression Grade	Weak N (%)	Moderate N (%)	Strong N (%)	Total
W-D SCC	37 (56.9%)	13 (20%)	0	50 (76.9%)
M-D SCC	3 (4.6%)	8 (12.3%)	2 (3.1%)	13 (20%)
P-D SCC	0	0	2 (3.1%)	2 (3.1%)
Total	40 (61.5%)	21 (32.3%)	4 (6.2%)	65 (100%)

According to grade, the expression of p53 was, well-differentiated SCCs show weak positivity and poorly differentiated SCCs show strong positivity. The p-value is < 0.01. This result is significant at $p < 0.05$. EGFR was expressed as membranous positivity, with few showing membranous and

cytoplasmic positivity. Most of the cases (36) showed weak EGFR expression with a score of 1 – 4, about 22 cases showed Moderate EGFR expression with a score of 5 – 8, and about 7 cases showed strong EGFR expression with a score of 9 – 12.

Table 7: Case distribution based on the site of SCC and grade of EGFR expression

EGFR Expression Site of tumor	Weak N (%)	Moderate N (%)	Strong N (%)	Total N (%)
Oral cavity	25 (38.46%)	14 (21.53%)	4 (6.15%)	43 (66.15%)
Oropharynx	5 (7.69%)	5 (7.69%)	2 (3.07%)	12 (18.46%)
Laryngopharynx	5 (7.69%)	2 (3.07%)	0	7 (10.76%)
Nasal cavity	0	0	1 (1.53%)	1 (1.53%)
Conjunctiva	0	1 (1.53%)	0	1 (1.53%)
Forehead	1 (1.53%)	0	0	1 (1.53%)
Total	36 (55.39%)	22 (33.84%)	7 (10.77%)	65 (100%)

The expression of EGFR in the oral cavity showed in 43 (66.15%) cases, out of these, 4 cases (6.15%) were showed strong EGFR positivity, 14 cases (21.53%) were showed moderate EGFR positivity and 25 cases (38.46%) were showed weak EGFR positivity. In the oropharynx, EGFR expression showed in 12 cases (18.46%), out of these, 2 cases (3.07%) showed strong EGFR positivity, 5 cases (7.69%) were showed moderate EGFR positivity and 5 cases (7.69%) were showed weak EGFR positivity. In the Laryngopharynx EGFR

expression showed in 7 cases (10.76%), out of these, 2 cases (3.07%) showed moderate EGFR positivity and 5 cases (7.69%) showed weak EGFR positivity. In the nasal cavity, EGFR expression showed in 1 case (1.53%), which was strong EGFR positivity. In conjunctiva, EGFR expression showed in 1 case (1.53%), which was moderate EGFR positivity. In Forehead EGFR expression showed in 1 case (1.53%), which was weak EGFR positivity.

Table 8: Case distribution based on Total Score of EGFR with tumor grade

EGFR Expression Grade	Weak N (%)	Moderate N (%)	Strong N (%)	Total N (%)
W-D SCC	29 (44.6%)	18 (27.7%)	3 (4.6%)	50 (77.1%)
M-D SCC	7 (10.8%)	4 (6.2%)	2 (3%)	13 (19.9%)
P-D SCC	0	0	2 (3%)	2 (3%)
Total	36 (55.39%)	22 (33.84%)	7 (10.77%)	65 (100%)

According to grade, the expression of EGFR, well-differentiated SCCs show weak positivity and poorly differentiated SCCs show strong positivity. The p-value is 0.0012. This result is significant at $p < 0.05$.

Discussion

Head and neck squamous cell carcinomas are a group of malignancies that can be predicted by TNM staging and IHC markers. The p53 tumor suppressor gene is inactivated in many HNSCCs, and mutations in p53 are associated with poor prognosis. p53 plays an important role in cell cycle control and apoptosis, and its inactivation can allow abnormal cells to proliferate and form cancer. Ceasing the increase in cellular growth halts the advancement of the cell cycle, thus preventing the replication of damaged DNA. While in this growth-arrested state, p53 has the potential to initiate the transcription of proteins that play a role in DNA repair. Apoptosis serves as a final option to prevent

the multiplication of cells that harbor abnormal DNA. The precise concentration of p53 within cells needs to be meticulously controlled. Despite its ability to suppress tumor formation, an elevated level of p53 might hasten the aging process due to excessive apoptosis. The primary controller of p53 is MDM2, which can initiate the breakdown of p53 using the ubiquitin system. [6, 7]

The p53 serves as an activator of transcription, overseeing the expression of various genes, including Mdm2 (to manage its regulation), as well as genes responsible for controlling growth arrest, DNA repair, and apoptosis. Functioning as a nuclear transcription factor, p53 triggers the activation of multiple target genes that participate in prompting cell cycle halt and/or apoptosis. In typical circumstances, p53 exhibits minimal expression, mainly due to proteasomal degradation mediated by the E3 ubiquitin-protein ligase MDM2, which has a RING-finger structure. This leads to p53's presence in a latent, functionally

inactive state. [8] Following instances of DNA damage, posttranslational modifications, such as phosphorylation and acetylation, prompt p53 to accumulate in the cell nucleus. These modifications transform p53 from a dormant state to an active one, possibly facilitated by the dissociation of MDM2 from p53. [9]

When p53 is in an active state, it transactivates a specific set of target genes that encourage cell cycle arrest and/or apoptosis, contingent on the extent and nature of the DNA damage. The cell cycle arrest orchestrated by p53 enables cells to undertake DNA repair. Once the DNA repair processes are finished, cells re-enter the regular cell cycle. Conversely, in situations where cells suffer severe DNA damage, p53 takes on its pro-apoptotic role, leading to the elimination of cells carrying substantial DNA damage. This action helps prevent the transmission of compromised DNA to progeny cells. As a result, p53 demonstrates its capacity to safeguard genomic integrity. [10, 11] p53 is a transcription factor that plays an important role in maintaining genomic integrity. Under normal conditions, p53 is expressed at a low level and is degraded by the protein MDM2. However, after DNA damage, p53 is activated and accumulates in the cell nucleus. Activated p53 can induce cell cycle arrest or apoptosis, depending on the severity of the DNA damage. Cell cycle arrest allows cells to repair damaged DNA, while apoptosis eliminates cells with serious DNA damage. [10, 11]

The current research indicates that out of the total cases, 40 exhibited weak staining, 25 displayed intermediate staining, and a strong staining pattern was observed in the remaining cases. In the study conducted by Hashmi AA et al. [12] the findings revealed that 13 cases had weak staining, while 78 cases demonstrated intermediate to strong staining. Similarly, Singla S et al. [13] found that among their subjects, 12 cases exhibited weak staining, and 28 cases showed intermediate to strong staining. In the study by Li Y et al. [14], results indicated that 19 cases had weak staining, and 32 cases had intermediate to strong staining. Lastly, the study conducted by Heah KG et al. [86] demonstrated that 9 cases exhibited weak staining, and 16 cases displayed intermediate to strong staining. Studies by Singla S et al. [13] p-value - < 0.001, Li Y et al. [14] (p-value - < 0.05), Heah KG et al. [15] p-value (< 0.05) demonstrated a statistically significant association between tumor grade of HNSCC and the p53 overexpression and those studies correlating with the present study (p-value < 0.01). A study by Hashmi AA et al. [12] (p - p-value - < 0.44) showed no such statistically significant association between the HNSCC and p53 overexpression. EGFR was the first discovered epidermal growth factor receptor.

EGFR is a protein that is involved in cell growth and proliferation. It is overexpressed in many types of cancer, including head and neck squamous cell carcinoma (HNSCC). EGFR signaling can lead to tumor growth and progression. [16, 17] EGFR activation is triggered by binding to growth factors. This binding leads to receptor dimerization, tyrosine kinase activity, and autophosphorylation. The activated EGFR then signals downstream to MAPK, Akt, and JNK pathways, which ultimately lead to DNA synthesis, cell proliferation, and differentiation. [18, 19] EGFR can also be internalized and degraded. This is a key step in down-regulating EGFR signaling. Stress conditions can induce ligand-independent endocytosis and degradation of EGFR. EGFR is an important biomarker for cancer. Its overexpression or mutations are associated with poor prognosis in HNSCC. Targeted therapies that inhibit EGFR signaling are being developed for the treatment of HNSCC and other cancers. [20]

About 80–90% of HNSCCs overexpress or harbor mutations in EGFR, and these alterations directly impact overall and progression-free survival. The increased expression of EGFR plays an important role in the prognosis of the disease. Most of the EGFR overexpressed HNSCCs are highly resistant to chemotherapy and radiotherapy. The present study found that 36 cases of HNSCC were weakly stained for EGFR, while 29 cases were intermediately or strongly stained. This is similar to the findings of other studies, such as Hashmi AA et al. [12] (27 weakly stained cases, 35 intermediately or strongly stained cases), Verma J et al. [21] (42 weakly stained cases, 6 intermediately or strongly stained cases), Zafar M et al. [22] (2 weakly stained cases, 50 intermediately or strongly stained cases), and Owusu-Afriyie et al. [23] (45 weakly stained cases, 42 intermediately or strongly stained cases). The results of these studies suggest that EGFR overexpression is common in HNSCC, but the degree of overexpression varies. This variation may be due to different factors, such as the tumor type, the patient's age, and the patient's overall health status.

Conclusion

The p53 and EGFR are two important genes that are frequently involved in the development of Head and Neck Squamous Cell Carcinoma (HNSCC). Alterations in these genes can have a significant impact on the prognosis and treatment response of patients with HNSCC. Mutation of Tp53 is the most common genetic abnormality in HNSCC, and it results in an accumulation and expression of p53 protein in tumor cells. p53 expression is a good prognostic marker for patients with HNSCC, and it can also be used to predict the response to chemoradiation therapy. EGFR is another important gene that is frequently involved in the development of HNSCC. EGFR signaling can promote tumor

growth and progression. EGFR overexpression or mutations are associated with poor prognosis in HNSCC. The clinical significance of p53 and EGFR alterations in relation to the HNSCC treatment is an area of active research. However, several studies have indicated that p53 and EGFR expression represent good prognostic parameters, and they can be used to predict the response to chemoradiation therapy.

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